

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Study of the Reaction between Vanadyl Sulphate and Rochelle Salt

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Spectrophotometric and conductometric studies of the reaction between vanadyl sulphate and Rochelle salt indicate that a coloured complex of composition 1:1 is formed. The system obeys Beer's law. The dissociation constant of the complex has been found to be 5.62×10^{-6} .

The fact that the bivalent vanadyl ion behaves in solution like metal ions has led to the study of its complex formation with malonic¹, oxalic², citric³, and salicylic⁴ acids. In the present investigation it has been observed that Rochelle salt (Na-K tartrate), when added to blue vanadyl salt solutions, produces a sharp colour change from blue to violet due to formation of a stable complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anal. R Rochelle salt and analysed sample of vanadyl sulphate (B.D.H.) were used; the solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Absorbance studies were made with a Beckman spectrophotometer and the *pH* and conductance measurements made on a glass electrode Beckman *pH* meter and Doran conductivity bridge, respectively. The experimental temperature was kept at 28° throughout the investigations.

Selection of Wave length.—The absorption spectra of mixtures of equimolar solutions (*M*/10) of vanadyl sulphate and the reagent in the ratios 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 have been represented in Fig. 1 (curves A, B and C.) It is seen that the colour produced has a maximum absorption at the wave length 775 μ . For further study therefore, the optical density measurements were made at or near this wave length.

Effect of Hydrogen-ion Concentration.—The absorbance of a mixture of vanadyl sulphate and Rochelle salt at wave length 775 μ was noted over a *pH* range of 2.3 to 5. The results shown in Fig. 2 indicate that the colour intensity reaches its maximum at *pH* 3.5 and then slowly decreases at higher *pH* values. The measurements were therefore made at the above *pH* (3.5), the *pH* of various solutions being adjusted by the addition of strong solutions of hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide as the case may be.

1. Bhattacharya and Banerji, *Curr. Sci.*, 1960, 29, 147.
2. Zolotavin and Kalugina, *Zhur. Obshchei Khim.*, 1956, 28, 1355.
3. *Idem.*, *Zhur. Neorg Khim.*, 1950, 1, 703.
4. Bhattacharya and Banerji, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 131.

Composition of the Complex.—Job's method of continued variation⁵, using equimolar ($M/10$) solutions each of vanadyl sulphate and Rochelle salt, was used for determination of the stoichiometry of the complex formed. The optical density measurements were carried out at wave lengths 725 $m\mu$, 775 $m\mu$, and 800 $m\mu$. In all the cases, the maxima in the curves (Fig. 3, curves A, B, and C), plotted between the difference in optical density and the frac-

FIG. 1. Equimol. ($M/10$) soln. of vanadyl sulphate and Rochelle salt. A (1:1), B (1:2), C (1:3).

FIG. 2. Variation of O.D. with pH of a 1:1 equimol. ($M/10$) mixture of vanadyl sulphate and R. salt.

FIG. 3. Composition of the complex by Job's method. A—at 725 $m\mu$. B—at 775 $m\mu$. C—800 $m\mu$

FIG. 4. A—Comp. of the complex (conduc.) by Job's method using $M/40$ equimol. soln. B—Dissociation const. of the complex using $M/60$ — $VOSO_4$ and $M/30$ —R. salt. C—Do, using $M/40$ R. salt and $M/80$ $VOSO_4$.

5. Job, *Ann. Chim.* 1926, *z*, 9, 113.

tion $[R]/\{[R]+[VO^{2+}]\}$ were obtained when $[R]/\{[R]+[VO^{2+}]\}$ equals 0.5, indicating the formation of a 1:1 complex between VO^{2+} and thereagent. The composition of the coloured compound was further confirmed to be 1:1 by applying Job's method to conductometric measurements (Fig. 4, curve A) using $M/40$ equimolar solutions of the reactants. The formula of the complex formed is suggested as $(VO C_4H_3O_6)^-$.

Stability of the Complex.—The addition of excess of alkali to the solution of the above complex does not yield any precipitate of vanadyl hydroxide, indicating thereby that the complex formed must be considerably stable. The dissociation constant, K , was determined conductometrically by the application of Job's method of continued variation using $M/60$ and $M/30$ solutions of vanadyl sulphate and Rochelle salt, respectively (Fig. 4, curve B). The experiment was repeated by taking $M/80$ vanadyl sulphate and $M/40$ Rochelle salt solutions. The experimental value of K comes to be 5.62×10^{-6} .

The validity of Beer's law was investigated at wave length 775 μ . A plot of the optical density against the concentration of the complex gives a straight line (Fig. 5), showing that the system obeys Beer's law even in concentrated solutions ($M/100$ to $M/10$).

FIG. 5. Validity of Beer's law.

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